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Research Article

**SYNTHESIS OF 5-{{(4-AMINO-N-[2-(DIETHYLAMINO)ETHYL]-
o-ANISAMIDO-5-YL}}-AMINO-3-SUBSTITUTEDIMINO-7-
SUBSTITUTEDIMINO-1,2,4,6-TRITHIAZEPINES.**

D. T. Tayade^{1*}, R. D. Thombare¹, S. A. Waghmare²

¹Department of Chemistry, Government Vidarbha Institute of Science and Humanities, Amravati 444606.

²Department of Chemistry, Ghulam Nabi Azad Arts, Comm. & Science College, Barshitakli, Dist. Akola 444401.

Abstract:

A novel series of 5-{{(4-amino-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamido-5-yl)-amino-3-substitutedimino-7-substitutedimino-1,2,4,6-trithiazepines was synthesized by the interactions of 4-amino-5-substituteddithiobiureto-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamides with phenylisothio carbamoyldichloride in acetone-ethanol medium. The structures of all the synthesized compounds were justified on the basis of chemical characteristics, elemental analysis and spectral studies.

Keywords: 5-{{(4-Amino-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamido-5-yl)-amino-3-phenylimino-7-ethylimino-1,2,4,6-trithiazepine, 4-amino-5-phenyldithiobiureto-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamide, phenylisothiocarbamoylchloride, acetone-ethanol medium.

Corresponding author:**D.T.Tayade,**

Department of Chemistry,
Government Vidarbha Institute of Science and Humanities,
Amravati 444606.

Email:- skdtayade@gmail.com,
rupalidhombare30@gmail.com.

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INTRODUCTION:

The literature survey reveals that heterocyclic compounds are used as drugs. It has been reported that the thiocarbamides exhibit antibacterial [1], fungicidal [2] insecticidal [3], antiviral [4], anesthetic [5] and have many biological activities. The most remarkable application of thiocarbamide is used as commercial pesticides, particularly herbicides [6-10]. Acyclic thiocarbamides were used as an intermediate for the synthesis of thiaziazepines. Recently we have synthesized 4-amino-5-substituted dithiobiureto-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamides. Due to significances of thiaziazepines in agricultural, medicinal, industrial and pharmaceutical sciences, it

was thought interesting to carry out cyclisation of 4-amino-5-substituted dithiobiureto-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamides in a new type of thiaziazepines.

In the present work 5-{(4-amino-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamido-5-yl)-amino-3-substituted dimino-7-substituted dimino-1,2,4,6-trithiazepines} was synthesized by the interactions of 4-amino-5-substituted dithiobiureto-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamides with phenylisothiocarbonyl dichloride in acetone-ethanol medium. The probable reaction and mechanism is depicted below (**Scheme-VI**),

Scheme- VI

R= t-butyl, phenyl, p-chlorophenyl, Ethyl, methyl, o-tolyl, m-tolyl, p-tolyl

Synthesis of 5-{{(4-amino-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamido-5-yl)-amino-3-phenylimino-7-ethylimino-1,2,4,6-trithiazepine
 5-{{(4-Amino-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamido-5-yl)-amino-3-phenylimino-7-ethylimino-1,2,4,6-trithiazepine was synthesized by the interaction of 4-amino-5-ethylthiobiureto-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamide and phenylisothiocarbonyl-chloride in acetone-ethanol

medium by refluxing on water bath for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was filtered in hot conditions. After distillation of excess solvent brownish yellow crystals were isolated, on basification with ammonia it gave 5-{{(4-amino-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamido-5-yl)-amino-3-phenylimino-7-ethylimino-1,2,4,6-trithiazepine. Yield 90%, m.p.223°C.

The probable reaction and mechanism depicted below,

Reaction

Table No. I-1

Sr. No.	Expt. No.	5-{(4-Amino-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamido-5-yl)-amino-3-substituted-imino-7-substitutedimino-1,2,4,6-trithiazepines	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)
1	(IIIb)	5-{(4-Amino-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamido-5-yl)-amino-3-phenylimino -7-methylimino-1,2,4,6-trithiazepine	80	219
2	(IIIc)	5-{(4-Amino-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamido-5-yl)-amino-3-phenylimino -7-t-butylimino-1,2,4,6-trithiazepine	85	221
3	(III d)	5-{(4-Amino-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamido-5-yl)-amino-3-phenylimino -7-p-Chlorophenylimino-1,2,4,6-trithiazepine	90	227
4	(IIIe)	5-{(4-Amino-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamido-5-yl)-amino-3-phenylimino -7-o-tolylimino-1,2,4,6-trithiazepine	92	230
5	(III f)	5-{(4-Amino-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamido-5-yl)-amino-3-phenylimino -7-m-tolylimino-1,2,4,6-trithiazepine	94	233
6	(IIIg)	5-{(4-Amino-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamido-5-yl)-amino-3-phenylimino -7-p-tolylimino-1,2,4,6-trithiazepine	89	240

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